

In our earlier report¹ we have illustrated the status of a species in a genus grown under saline soil from the studies of three mangrove species of *Avicennia* (Fam. Verbenaceae). Now we want to communicate our findings on a species, yet unexamined, of another mangrove genus *Carapa* with a view to compare the results published earlier by different workers.

Literature on genus *Carapa* revealed the presence of Deacetoxy-7-oxogedunin², Carapin³ in *C. procera* and 6 α -11 β -diacetoxy gedunin⁴, 11 β -acetoxy gedunin⁴, andirobin^{5,6}, 7-deacetoxy-7-oxogedunin^{5,6} in *C. guianensis* and gedunin⁷, xylocarpin⁷, methyl 3- β -acetoxy-1-oxomeliac-8,30-enate⁷, β -sitosterol⁷ in *Xylocarpus* (syn. *Carapa*) *granatum*. Plant material for investigation was collected from Sundarban (West Bengal).

Petroleum extract of the air dried bark was concentrated. The ether soluble portion of the petroleum extract was further separated into neutral and acidic part. The acidic part yielded no triterpene acid. The neutral fraction on chromatography over silica gel G furnished the following compounds.

The first fraction was a white crystalline solid m.p. 248°; $[\alpha] +71^\circ$; ν_{max} 1715 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl); M.S. m/e 426 (M⁺), 411 (M⁺-CH₃), 302 (cleavage of ring D at 13-18 and 14-15 bonds), 218 and 232 and 246 (species 205 with one, two and three additional carbon atom), 205, 191, 189; NMR. (δ) 0.79-1.5 (methyl and methylene protons), 2.32 (α -keto methylene); oxime m.p. 285°. The compound was reduced to a compound m.p. 268°; M.S. m/e 428 (M⁺), 413 (M⁺-CH₃), 395 (413-H₂O), 304 (cleavage of ring D), 275, 207. This mass fragmentation pattern were in complete conformity with that of epifriedelinol. All these data showed the presence of friedelin which was finally confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Second fraction was triacontanol, m.p. 80°.

Third fraction, a shining crystalline solid m.p. 138°, ν_{max} 3520 (hydroxyl) and 1649 cm⁻¹ (double bond), showed bluish-violet coloration with Liebermann-Burchard reagent (test for sterol). Mass spectrum of this compound registered two molecular ion peaks, one at m/e 414 and other at 412 which showed the solid to be a sterol mixture. The genesis of other peaks can be evaluated as m/e 396 (414-18) and 394 (412-18), 255 (396-C₁₀H₂₁ or 394-C₁₀H₁₉). The compound with ring double bond and saturated C₁₀H₂₁ side chain corresponding to molecular ion m/e 414 was β -sitosterol and the other one with C₁₀H₁₉ side chain was identical in all respects with stigmasterol.

Last fraction, a heavy amorphous solid, registered an intense spot at R_f 0.7 which on further purification through exhaustive preparative tlc yielded a crystalline material m.p. 290°; ν_{max} 1760 (ester carbonyl), 1715 (ring ketone), 1660 cm⁻¹ (double bond). The mass fragmentation pattern clearly indicated it to be a mixture having tetra-nortriterpene skeleton with M⁺ at m/e 542 and m/e 514. The other mass peaks were at m/e 499, 472, 470, 454, 439, 426, 411, 395, 385, 201, 187, 173. The compound was a mixture (A) of methyl 3 β -isopropyl-1-oxo-

meliacate and methyl 3 β -acetoxy-1-oxo-meliacate. NMR data on this mixture is awaiting. Due to paucity of materials a good NMR was not available. We want to report the NMR data in our subsequent papers on 'the effect of ecology on biosynthetic route'.

Petroleum extract of *C. obovata* leaves on similar treatment as previously described, yielded Friedelin, β -sitosterol, Stigmasterol and a mixture of two tetranortriterpenoids (A).

From the earlier report²⁻⁷ and also from present investigation it is evident that the biosynthetic pattern of all the species in the genus *Carapa* is somewhat uniform.

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References

1. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated)
2. C. W. L. BEVAN, J. W. POWELL and D. A. H. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 980.
3. E. O. ARENE, C. W. L. BEVAN, J. W. POWELL and D. A. H. TAYLOR, *Chem. Comm.*, 1965, 14, 302.
4. J. D. CONNOLLY, R. MCCRINDLE, K. H. OVERTON and J. FEENEY, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 22, 891.
5. W. D. OLLIS, A. D. WARD and R. ZELNIK, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 37, 2607.
6. W. D. OLLIS, A. D. WARD, H. M. DEOLIVEIRA and R. ZELNIK, *Tetrahedron*, 1970, 26, 1637.
7. D. A. OKORIE and D. A. H. TAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc. (C)*, 1970, 2, 211.

Studies on Adsorption Indicators. Part I. Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenyl phthalides as Adsorption Indicators in Argentometric Titrations of Iodide Ions

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THE use of phenolphthalein as adsorption indicator in slightly alkaline condition is highly recommended in literature by Uzumasa and Miyake¹.

In the present communication the studies have been extended to seven other similar and unsymmetrical phthaloids (Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenylphthalides). Thus, 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I), 3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II), 3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III), 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV), 3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)2:3-naphthalide (V), β -1-naphthyl-phenolsuccinoin (VI), and β -2-naphthylphenolsuccinoin (VII) have been studied for their utility as adsorption indicators in the argentometric titrations of iodide ions.

NOTES

Experimental

Materials : AgNO₃ (A.R., BDH) and KI (Thomas & Thomas, Indian) were used.

Indicator solution : A 0.2% of each dye was prepared in rectified spirit; 3-8 drops of each indicator (depending on the concentration of the solution) were used for every 10 ml of the solution titrated.

Preparation of the dyes : The dyes were prepared by the methods I and III,² II (by condensing tetrachlorophthalic anhydride with phenol in presence of a few drops of conc. H₂SO₄), IV³, V⁴, VI and VII⁵.

Procedure : AgNO₃ has been added from the burette shaking the contents of the conical flask, coagulation took place at the end point.

Results and Discussion

The red coloured dye (I) has absorption maxima of 5300 Å (in both neutral as well as alkaline condition)². In neutral medium (I) can be easily used for solutions ranging in dilution from 0.1N-0.0025N. For 0.00125N solution it requires vigorous shaking at the end point; while in slightly alkaline medium it can be used up to 0.01 solution only. Dyes II-V show adsorbility in slightly alkaline condition (using NH₄OH till a slight pink or violet colour develops). II like phenolphthalein and I, can be used for solutions 0.1-0.0025N; with 0.00125N solutions all the

dyes I, II, and phenolphthalein require vigorous shaking even at the end point. III can be used for solutions 0.1-0.01N; IV and V for solutions 0.1-0.05N.

Detailed studies of the indicator dyes I and II have been shown in the Table.

The adsorbility and colour changes of the dyes (I-V) have been compared with phenolphthalein as follows :

3-(p-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I) : Titrations easily possible for solutions 0.1-0.0025N in neutral medium; and for solutions 0.1-0.01N in slightly alkaline condition. Suspension (violet shaded yellow solution) → Orange ppt.

3,3-bis(p-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II) : Titrations easily possible for solutions 0.1-0.0025N. Suspension (violet shaded yellow soln.) → Orange-yellow to pink ppt.

3-acetyl-3-(o- or p-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III) : Suspension (pink tinged yellow with solutions 0.1-0.05N) → Orange-yellow ppt.

3-(o-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) : Suspension (violet shaded yellow with solutions 0.1-0.05N) → violet shaded ash ppt.

3-phenyl-3-(o- or p-hydroxyphenyl) 2 : 3-naphthalide (V) : Orange-pink tinged yellow with solutions 0.1-0.05N) → violet-pink shaded orange ppt.

TABLE—DYES I (USED IN NEUTRAL) AND II (USED IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE CONDITION) AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS. VOLUME OF KI TAKEN FOR TITRATION : 10 ml

Dye	Concn. of KI	Vol. and concn. of AgNO ₃	Drops of indicator	Transition of colour	Remarks
I	0.1N	10.00 ml 0.1N	10	yellow suspn. → orange-yellow ppt.	complete coagulation and clear supernatant liquid at the exact end point.
I	0.02N	10.00 ml 0.02N	10	orange-yellow soln. → pink ppt	same as above.
I	0.01N	10.00 ml 0.01N	6	yellow soln. → pink ppt.	same as above.
I	0.005N	10.01 ml 0.005N	5	orange tinged yellow suspn. → orange ppt.	same as above.
I	0.0025N	10.02 ml 0.0025N	4	yellow suspn. → orange ppt.	same as above.
I	0.00125N	10.02 ml 0.00125N	3	orange-yellow soln. → orange ppt.	requires good shaking; supernatant same as above.
II	0.02N	10.00 ml	6	violet shaded soln. → pink ppt.	same as above.
II	0.01N	10.00 ml 0.01N	6	yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	same as above.
II	0.005N	10.00 ml 0.005N	4	yellow suspn. → pink ppt.	same as above.
II	0.0025N	10.00 ml 0.0025N	4	violet shaded soln. → pink ppt.	same as above.
II	0.00125N	10.00 ml 0.00125N	3	violet shaded soln. → pink ppt.	coagulation requires much shaking; supernatant liquid same as above.

The following points emerge on comparing the above dyes (I and II) with phenolphthalein :

Titration of iodide ions against silver ions : With 0.1*N* KI solution the adsorption indicators I, II and phenolphthalein show the coagulation of the slightly coloured (orange or pinkish or violet shaded-yellow) ppt. With 0.02*N* solutions the coagulated ppt. is more pronounced in adsorbility. With 0.01*N*-0.005*N* solutions dye I seems to have adsorbed better than II and phenolphthalein. With 0.0025*N* solutions I shows good orange ppt, II and phenolphthalein shows good pink ppt. The dyes I, II, and phenolphthalein can also be used for 0.00125*N* solution but coagulation takes place after shaking the solution well at the end point.

Conclusion

3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I) is in some respects better than phenolphthalein as it can be used in neutral (0.1-0.00125*N* solutions) and as well as in alkaline (0.1-0.01*N* solutions) conditions; with solutions 0.01-0.005*N* it seems to have adsorbed better. Dyes III-V, can only be used for higher concentration of the solutions (0.1-0.05*N*). Dyes VI and VII are unsuitable as adsorption indicators.

References

1. Y. UZUMASA and Y. MIYAKE, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1933, 54, 1043; *Chem. Abs.*, 1934, 28, 985.
2. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 676.
3. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1972, 7, 359.
4. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1972, 27b, 405.
5. E. SINGH and P. C. GUPTA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1971, 6, 427.

Studies on Adsorption Indicators. Part II. Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenylphthalides as Adsorption Indicators in Argentometric Titrations of Chloride Ions

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MEHROTRA¹ has reported the use of phenolphthalein (in slightly alkaline condition) as adsorption indicator for the titration of chloride ions.

In the present communication the studies have been extended to seven new similar and unsymmetrical phthalides* (Mono- and bis-hydroxyphenylphthalides). Thus, 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide

(I), 3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II), 3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III), 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV), 3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)2 : 3-naphthalide (V), β -1-naphthyl-phenolsuccinein (VI), and β -2-naphthyl-phenolsuccinein (VII) have been studied for their utility as adsorption indicators in the argentometric titrations of chloride ions.

Experimental

Materials used : AgNO₃ and NaCl used were A.R. (BDH) grade reagents.

Indicator solution, Preparation of the dyes, and Procedure see².

Results and Discussion

The dye (I) red in colour, has absorption maxima of 5300 Å (both in neutral and alkaline condition)³. In the neutral medium it can be easily used as an indicator for solutions ranging in dilution from 0.1-0.005*N* but in slightly alkaline condition it can only be used in solutions 0.1-0.02*N*. II, like phenolphthalein and I can be easily used for solutions 0.1-0.005*N*. For solutions 0.004-0.0025*N*, I, II, and phenolphthalein can be used if the solutions are vigorously shaken even after the end point is reached. III can be used for solutions 0.1-0.02*N*. IV and V can be used for 0.1*N* dilution only. VI and VII are unsuitable.

Detailed studies of dyes I and II as adsorption indicators are shown in the Table.

The adsorbility and colour changes of the dyes (I-V) have been compared with phenolphthalein as follows :

3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) phthalide (I) : Titrations easily possible in neutral medium for solutions 0.1-0.005*N*; in alkaline condition for solutions 0.1-0.02*N*. Suspension (white with orange tinge) → pink; orange-pink; and orange ppt.

3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (II) : Titrations easily possible for solutions 0.1-0.005*N*. Suspension (pinkish white or violet soln.) → violet ppt.

3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide (III) : Titrations possible for 0.1-0.02*N* solutions. Suspension (white with violet tinge) → light violet ppt.

3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl) 4,5-dimethoxyphthalide (IV) : Titration possible for 0.1*N* solution only. Suspension (orange shaded-white) → violet-ash ppt.

3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)2 : 3-naphthalide (V) : Titration possible for 0.1*N* solution. Suspension (white with pink tinge) → ash coloured ppt.

Conclusion

The following points emerge on comparing the above dyes (I and II) with phenolphthalein :

*Part I, see *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 948.